

Primary Study on Spatial Distribution of Swiftlet Farming in Myeik

San San Khine *

Abstract

Swiftlet farming, one of famous services of Myeik where is a well-known place as a supply area of bird's nest for Myanmar. This farming has been steadily increasing every year since the last decade because the demand for bird's nest has been increased. The development of swiftlet farm from 2005 until present time period is described. The research question is that why the swiftlets are concentrated in southern part of Thanintharyi Region, especially in Myeik. Moreover, the concentrated area of this industry is found along the Strand Road in Naukle and Dewaisu ward, the west-southern coastal area of Myeik. This paper is mainly emphasized on the concentrated area of swiftlet farming houses and to find out the concentrated causes of swiftlet farming houses from the geographic point of view. Moreover, the ranks of this industry are divided by the building size and production of edible bird's nest. The depending causes for the different ranks of this industry are presented. The weak and strong points of bird nest's industry are pointed out to promote these industries.

Introduction

Swiftlet farming is an important service for Myeik because its products are governing as the town localization product. Moreover, the swiftlets are found only in the southern part of Thanintharyi Region, especially in Myeik, Kyunsu, Bokepyin and Kawthaung townships. compartment area for swiftlet conservation which is about 1171 acres in Myeik Archipelago is being controlled by the Forest Department. The conservation areas on Myeik Archipelago are Mali Kyun compartment(918 acres) in Palaw Township, Longlone conservation area (216 acres) in Launglone Township, Yeaye bird nest Kyun (498 acres) in Kyunsu Township, Bokepyin bird nest compartment area (53 acres) in Bokepyin Township and Kawthaung conservation area (33 acres) in Kawthaung. The natural bird's nest were produced from caves of these compartment areas by controlling of Padamyar Yaung Chi Co-ltd. Additionally artificial swiftlet farming houses are opened in Myeik and Kawthaung towns which are controlled by house owners. Swiftlet farming houses are only houses which are situated in settlement area and some are mixed by dwellers. Most houses are found upstairs which differ from the first floor, second floor until fifth floor. People settle in the downstairs of houses and swiftlets roost upstairs of dwellers. As Swiftlets don't like smell and smoke from cooking, dwellers should avoid smoke and smell.

* Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University.

Plate.1 foreground: Stores on Floor Space
Back ground: Upstairs (third floors and upper)
Swiftlet Farming House

Plate.2 Artificial Swiftlet Farming House as
Cave

Plate. 3 One Entrance of Swiftlets and natural Swiftlet Farming Houses

Research Question

Why are the swiftlet concentrated in southern part of Thanintharyi Region, especially in Myeik. Moreover, the concentrated area of this firm is found along the Strand Road in Naukle and Dewaisu ward, the west-southern coastal area of Myeik.

Objectives

The major objective of this research is to show the different attractive styles for coming of swiftlets which cause the variation of the edible bird's nest production.

Data Collection and Methodology

The first, personal interviews with fifteen owners of swiftlets farming houses were done and the informal discussion with the manager of Padamyar Yaung Chi Co., Ltd was made. The secondary data such as location of bird's nest industries, established year,

differences of machine using to attract for coming swiftlets and natural coming swiftlets and increasing of swiftlets farming houses from 2004 until 2012 were derived from Forest Department in Myeik. The GIS method is used for dividing the distribution of swiftlets farming houses and classification of rank of these farms.

General Description of Study Area

Myeik is located in the southern part of Thanintharyi Region, southern Myanmar. This township is situated between 12° 13' and 12 ° 45' north latitude and 98 ° 30' and 98 ° 55' east longitudes. The western part of this town is occupied with Andaman Sea, which cover with Myeik Archipelago. Indonesia produces about 70 per cent of the world's bird's nest, followed by Malaysia with 20 per cent, and Thailand. The location of Myeik is 50 miles far from Thailand and its location is suitable to settle and built of swiftlet farming houses.

Myeik Town is located on the eastern bank of Myeik River. Most area of Myeik is distributed on lowland level. But some area can be found with undulation and alluvial foundation. Myeik lies the western spurs of Thanintharyi Yoma and adjoining hills can be found in this Town. The alignment of hilly upland area lies from southwest to northeast direction.

The latitudinal location designates that this area lies within the tropic and this area locate near equatorial environment and near the ocean. Its temperature is high because its location falls in tropic zone. The normal maximum mean temperature recorded at Myeik weather station is 31.6 °C. The maximum temperature occurred in April with 34.59°C and in August with 29.06 °C the minimum temperature in January with 21.06 °C and 28.83 °C in March. Influence of temperature is protected by installing of air conditioner, it is found in some swiftlets farming houses. According to Koppen classification, the climatic condition of study area obtains a tropical monsoon climate.

As Myeik is located in the eastern bank of Bay of Bengal and lies on windward direction of monsoon, this town receives intense and heavy rainfall. The average annual rainfall is 4207 millimeters the period between 2002 and 2012. The highest rain fall months May, June, July, August and September which receive 3525 millimeters or 83.79% of annual rainfall.

According to informal talk with skill persons within conservation area, swiftlets from compartment area in Myeik region move other regions from July until October because heavy and intense rainfall prevalence to unfit for swiftlet living in caves. But, swiftlets lived in houses' roost in year round because houses can cover moisture and heavy rainfall.

Depending on the soil and climatic conditions such as rainfall and temperature, the varieties of flora and fauna occur. The major dominant forest is evergreen forest which exists on the higher elevation and lowland area of surrounding area of Myeik. The second dominant species are tidal forest or mangrove forest which distributed along the coastal area of Kyunsu and Myeik. But, most of these forest areas are gradually decreased by extension of garden land, rubber plantation and logging. Due to these forests encourage and give many ways as ecosystem providing and nutrients for these swiftlets, degradation of these forest need to conserve.

Figure 1 The Location Map Of Myeik Town in Thanintharyi Division and Swiftlet Framing's Location in Myeik Town,
 Source; Land Record Department and Forest Department in Myeik Town

Table 1 Temperature and Rainfall Condition in Myeik Town (from 2002 to 2012)

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	June	July	August	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total/ Ave
MaxTem °C	32.71	32.92	33.66	34.59	31.62	30.34	29.09	29.06	29.99	30.98	32.71	32.46	31.67
Mean Tem °C	26.88	27.99	31.24	29.73	28.16	27.25	26.43	26.385	26.85	27.32	27.93	26.91	27.87
Minimum Tem °C	21.06	23.06	28.83	24.87	24.71	24.16	23.78	23.71	23.71	23.66	23.16	21.37	24.06
Rainfall (mm)	29	46	90	123	593	640	881	789	622	330	30	34	4207

Source: Meteorology and Hydrology Department, Dawei

Figure 2 Temperature and Rainfall Condition in Myeik Town (from 2002 to 2012)

Source: Based on Table 1

Character and Habitat of Swiftlet

Swiftlet produces a bird's nest that is eaten by people for healthy diet. In Myeik, white-nest swiftlet (*Aerodramus fuciphagus*) species and black-nest swiftlet species (*Aerodramus maximus*) are mainly found. Most of these birds are 10 cm long from head to tail-tip and about 7 grams in weight. Their legs are too short and weak for walking or perching, but their feet have sharp and re-curved claws, excellently adapted to cling to the stony surface of cave wall. (Lim Chan Koon and etal,2002).

Caves from some Myeik Archipelago and some houses within Myeik are created by natural roosting and nesting site of these swiftlet but they find food completely outside of these houses and caves. Swiftlets naturally live in group. The swiftlet groups begin to leave as early as at 6:00 a.m in the morning and return to at 6:00 p.m in the afternoon. They catch their food in the sky nearly the entire day and they return down at 3:00 to 4:00 p. m.

Plate 4 Swiftlet bird (Back and tail dark, rump very slightly paler)

Plate 5 Constructed condition of Bird's nest in Houses

The nest is also a self-supporting structure, half-bowl in shape. The nest cup is built thin and irregular laminae of edible nest cement. The floor of nest cup has the irregular network lines and small contour feathers of swiftlet plumage. There are two types of bird's nest in Myeik namely white bird's nest and black bird's nest.

Plate. 6 Bird's Nests

Swiftlet coming Patterns for Roosting

There are two different kinds for swiftlet coming into houses in Myeik namely natural and artificial swiftlet farming houses. These two types of swiftlet farming houses are scattered on the south-western part of Myeik and total amount of swiftlet farming houses with bird nest built about 51. They are 19 in Daweisu, 7 in Seiknge, 7 in Talinesu, 6 in Myitnge, each 4 in Kangyi and Naukle, each 2 in Kanpyar and Saytan wards.

Natural Swiftlet Farming Houses

According to Field study and questionnaire experience for farming, the best choosing place of swiftlet for roosting and construct bird's nest entirely related with the suitable climate and environment, protected place for threatening of swiftlet and upright concrete foundation and large tall building as cavern like situation. The fresh and cool air from the sea easily blows these farming houses and the houses' temperature is suitable for swiftlet birds' living. But, some believe that the construction of bird nest in buildings is associated the luck of house owners. Swiftlet naturally roosting are set up six houses in Myeik, these houses don't use sound machine to come swiftlets which is naturally originated. All natural swiftlet farming houses can be found along the bank of sea coast, four in Daweisu ward, one in Naukle and one in Talinesu ward. The products of bird's nest from natural farming obviously exceed products from artificial swiftlet farming houses.

Artificial Swiftlet Farming Houses

Although some business persons need to make up naturally the bird's nest, swiftlets don't come as they expect. Therefore, they install swiftlet sonar with same sound as swiftlet tune in farming home which attract these birds. The charges of electricity installing machine are usually about 90000 kyats per one month. Even if Swiftlet come into farming home, they created bird's nest after installing machines for two years. Some lucky home is long time period about only two months for creation for bird's nest. After creation of bird's nest by swiftlets, owners remove the sound machine. However swiftlets come into those homes after removing sound machine because their nests were made. Sound machine used houses are about 60 but these birds come into only 45 houses of Myeik .Most artificial swiftlet houses are found

in 15 or 34% of total artificial swiftlet houses within Myeik in Dewaisu and 7 houses or 17% of total artificial houses in Seiknge and each 6 in Talinsu and Myitnge wards.

Improvement of Swiftlets' Farming Houses and Production

Swiftlets farming houses had come out in Myeik since 1980 but it did not use machine to call swiftlets. These birds came and constructed bird's nest into a houses which is located along sea coast of downtown of Myeik and it had no dwellers. From 2004 to 2006, there were only two bird's nest industries and production as 7.5 visses in Myeik. In that time, the swiftlets came and constructed the bird's nest naturally and there was no man-made repairing. Bird nest industries increased to 17 houses and the production increased to 10.6 visses in 2007. The causes of increasing of houses related with using swiftlet sonar. Moreover, edible bird nests are becoming more and more popular as the most expensive foods for the sick make the owners get high income.

Figure 3 The Distribution of Natural and Artificial Swiftlet Farming Houses (2013)

Source: Forest Department in Myeik

In 2008, the bird's nest farms rose to 33, which produced about 12.69 visses. From 2009 to 2012, these farms had about 42 but these amounts indicated to only actual product farms. But the production varied in those period 14.3498 visses in 2009-2010, 38.6198 in 2010-2011 and 17.6375 visses in 2011-2012.

Table 2 Distribution of Artificial and natural swiftlet farming Houses by Wards

Ward's Name	Artificial Houses	Percent of AS	Natural Houses	Percent of NS	Total
Dawaisu	15	34	4	66.66	19
Seiknge	7	16	-		7
Talinesu	6	13	1	16.67	7
Myitnge	6	13	-		6
Kangyi	4	9	-		4
Naukle	3	7	1	16.67	4
Kanpyar	2	4.5	-		2
Saytan	2	4.5	-		2
Kalwin	1	2.2	-		1
Total	45	100	6	100	51

Source; Forest Department in Myeik Town

Table 3 Increasing of Numbers of Swiftlet Farming Houses and Production of Bird's Nest (From 2004 to 2013)

Year	No. of swiftlet farming houses	No.of actual product houses	Production (viss)
2004-05	8	2	7.5
2005-06	11	2	7.5
2006-07	37	2	10.6
2007-08	46	17	11.59
2008-09	52	33	12.69
2009-10	58	42	14.3498
2010-11	60	42	38.6198
2011-12	68	42	17.6375
2012-13	71	50	26.123

Source; Forest Department in Myeik

Figure 4 Increasing of Bird's Nest Industries and Production from 2004 to 2013

Source; Based on Table 3

Products of bird's nest by houses

The production of bird nest varies in dissimilar houses, the first rank production bird nest house is located along the sea as natural swiftlet farming and had made since 1980. This house produces bird nest over six visses. The data of production of each swiftlet farming houses get from Forest Department and the products were separated into three categories such as high products houses, medium products houses and low products houses.

The houses produced about one viss and above that defined as high production rank class. There are five houses in high products, among them, three in Daweisu and two in Naukle ward. These houses are found with four natural swiftlet farming houses but only one natural house remains in low production. Therefore, about 80 % of natural swiftlet houses yielded the high production of bird's nest.

The medium product of bird's nest is expressed by roughly from half viss to under one viss in yields. These houses have about eleven which distributed three in Daweisu ward, two in Talinesu and another two in Saytan ward. Every one medium product is set up in Naukle, Kangyi and Kalwin ward. Among them, ten or 91% of total medium product houses are from artificial swiftlet farming houses.

The lowest product swiftlet houses are described by under 0.5 viss of bird's nest produced house which have about 34 houses or 60% of total houses. Therefore, the lowest product houses are in number great 12 houses in Daweisu, six in Myitnge, each five in Seiknge and Talinesu wards. All of these products houses contain in artificial swiftlet farming houses.

Figure 5 .The Distribution of Different Bird's Nest Products

Source : Forest Department in Myeik

Swiftlet Farming Houses by established years

The established years diverge from 1980 until 2009. The swiftlets' farming house was taking place one in 1980. This farming increased to two in 1983 because new one was opened in this year. In that time, swiftlet farms were created naturally. In 2004, other two farms again were organized and in that time there were only four farms in Myeik. In 2006, 34 farms were established and the total amount increased to 38 farms. Other two farms were built in 2009 and the total amount of all farms has 53 houses in present time. According to enterprise's licenses to Forest Department, swiftlet farming houses will increase because about 18 swiftlet farming houses in Myeik have installed song sonars and it is predictable that these houses will produce bird nest in the future. Therefore, there are 71 swiftlet farming houses in the whole town.

Figure 6 a. Distribution of Swiftlet Farms by Depending on Established Year
 b. Distribution of Swift farming Houses After 2011 (Dot Red Colour)

Source : Forest Department in Myeik

Swiftlet farming Houses' Size

Houses' sizes differ from 100 square-feet to 5500 square-feet in Myeik. Moreover the height of house can vary from one floor house until five levels houses. The swiftlet farming houses have size from 80 square-feet to 360 square feet that comprise eight farming houses. The houses size from 361square feet until 1125 square feet have about 19 houses and eleven houses are sizable from about 1126 square feet to 1650 square feet. Three swiftlet farming houses are sizable from 2251 square-feet to 5500 square-feet. According to Spearman's rank correlation method, the correlation between the products of bird's nest of each houses and house's sizes has -0.09 which indicated there is low degree of negative between two sets of data.

Figure. 7. The Distribution of Swiftlet Farming Houses by Ranks of Sizes

Source: Forest Department in Myeik

Trade

Bird nest is light in weight and small in bulk, can be stored for rather long periods. Yangon is the leading, accounting for about 75 percent of total product. Some person who has no bird nest carrying permit can't carry over 0.05 viss to other regions due to controlling of Forest Department. There is no international trade of bird nest.

The bird nest and its products from Padamyar Yaung Chi Co-ltd (Bird's nest Enterprise) is one of the best bird nest distribution Enterprise which extracted natural bird nest from caves of four compartment areas in Thanintharyi Region. The bird nest selling and distribution centers are situated in Yangon.

The price of bird's nest differ from different quality which depends on bird's nest colors, white colour states as first class, second class as white and brown mix with brown color feathers and third class defines brown and black color. One viss of first class bird's nest was paid 35 lakhs and other classes under 30 lakhs in 2007. The price of natural bird's nest from caves of swiftlets islands had about from 40 lakhs until 50 lakhs in 2007. The price of bird's nest is great and 35lakhs for one viss in 2011. But the price of bird's nest remains in variable, about 27 lakhs in 2013.

Conclusion and Suggestion

The location factor of Myeik, which is located in low latitude and coastal portion, is the vital reason for coming of swiftlet. It lies on between 12° 13' and 12 ° 45' north latitude and 98 ° 30' and 98 ° 55' east longitudes, which is southern part of Myanmar. The some coastal area of this town fill land and some houses were constructed on these land fill area. Climate such as similar equatorial climate and vegetation with dominant evergreen forest are the support ant facts for swiftlets farming. The natural bird nest buildings in cave of Mali Kyun

compartment, Longlone conservation area, Yeaye bird nest Kyun, Bokeyyin bird nest compartment area in Myeik Archipelago are designated as the suitable reasons for swiftlet farming houses in Myeik. Moreover, the natural bird nest construction in houses in Myeik Town causes to set up swiftlet farming houses. Due to above mentioned conditions encouraged and attracted for coming of swiftlets, knowledge and awareness of environmental conservation for tropical rainforest and watershed area within Thanintharyi Division and ecosystem of swiftlet should share to local people and authority persons.

The longstanding and good foundation concrete buildings were constructed in southwestern part of this town which located coastal part of town. Therefore, most of swiftlet farming houses are concentrated in this part of town. But, systematic research for the suitable and influence and avoid, improper factors of swiftlets should be done and the result should be shared to swiftlet farming owners and local people.

The market scope and value of bird's nest are effective reasons for swiftlet farming. Moreover the ten percent of bird's nest products as tax must pay to Forest Department and some don't want to pay therefore paying tax should be prepared to raise owners' spirits and more effective and increasing of farming.

The owners and entrepreneurs should do to promote the large sizable firms or companies as international stages which prepare from the stage of simple bird nest collection of houses to developed stages such as ready-made food steps or other preparing goods by using more effective methods. These methods are derived giving trainings to staffs and employees by inviting advisors and more experience or skill persons from foreign.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank specially Head and staffs from Forest Department, Padamyar Yaung Chi Co-ltd and some swiftlet farming owners for help to get some data. We also offer think to Daw Than Than Aye, lecturer, English Department, University of Myeik, for checking in English Grammar and Myo Win (Thrd year, Geography specialization, University of Myeik) for help during the field study period.

References

Lim Chan Koon and Earl of Cranbrook(2002). *Swiftlets of Borneo (Builders of Edible Nests)*. Natural History Publications (Borneo), Kota Kiabalu.

၂၀၁၆ ခုနှစ်

၂၀၁၆ ခုနှစ် (၂၀၁၆) / မြန်မာ့သမိုင်းနှင့် ဗဟိုဘဏ်နှင့် နေပြည်တော်